

Table 1. Parameters of the fundamental QPO in the PDS derived from NICER data

Obs ID	day [†]	$\nu_{0:\text{QPO1}}$ (Hz)	Δ_{QPO1} (Hz)	rms _{QPO1} (%)	Q _{QPO1}	σ_{QPO1}
6203980102	2.52	0.369 ^{+0.012} _{-0.026}	0.047 ^{+0.053} _{-0.031}	5.63 ^{+2.73} _{-1.40}	7.90 ^{+9.23} _{-5.86}	2.02
6203980104	4.06	0.780 ^{+0.010} _{-0.009}	0.129 ^{+0.022} _{-0.025}	9.55 ^{+0.48} _{-0.70}	6.05 ^{+1.10} _{-1.24}	6.81
6203980105	5.04	0.888 ^{+0.005} _{-0.005}	0.121 ^{+0.014} _{-0.012}	8.86 ^{+0.27} _{-0.28}	7.35 ^{+0.89} _{-0.80}	16.10
6703010101	5.55	0.865 ^{+0.008} _{-0.008}	0.117 ^{+0.014} _{-0.014}	9.20 ^{+0.38} _{-0.22}	7.41 ^{+0.98} _{-0.93}	20.90
6203980106	6.01	1.128 ^{+0.006} _{-0.005}	0.194 ^{+0.014} _{-0.013}	8.78 ^{+0.17} _{-0.18}	5.80 ^{+0.43} _{-0.41}	24.84
6203980107	7.54	1.125 ^{+0.006} _{-0.006}	0.168 ^{+0.014} _{-0.013}	8.84 ^{+0.22} _{-0.22}	6.69 ^{+0.59} _{-0.56}	19.65
6203980108	8.00	1.234 ^{+0.004} _{-0.004}	0.174 ^{+0.010} _{-0.010}	8.56 ^{+0.14} _{-0.15}	7.10 ^{+0.44} _{-0.42}	29.45
6203980109	9.03	1.256 ^{+0.004} _{-0.004}	0.192 ^{+0.009} _{-0.008}	8.56 ^{+0.12} _{-0.12}	6.53 ^{+0.31} _{-0.30}	35.98
6203980110	10.52	1.305 ^{+0.004} _{-0.004}	0.162 ^{+0.009} _{-0.008}	8.27 ^{+0.14} _{-0.14}	8.07 ^{+0.47} _{-0.44}	28.71
6203980111	11.04	1.173 ^{+0.004} _{-0.004}	0.172 ^{+0.009} _{-0.008}	8.36 ^{+0.14} _{-0.14}	6.80 ^{+0.37} _{-0.35}	30.16
6703010103	11.35	1.127 ^{+0.006} _{-0.006}	0.150 ^{+0.017} _{-0.016}	8.38 ^{+0.26} _{-0.26}	7.53 ^{+0.91} _{-0.84}	16.07
6203980112	12.06	1.029 ^{+0.010} _{-0.009}	0.107 ^{+0.023} _{-0.020}	8.38 ^{+0.49} _{-0.52}	9.59 ^{+2.14} _{-1.84}	8.10
6203980112	12.20	1.091 ^{+0.022} _{-0.020}	0.085 ^{+0.037} _{-0.037}	8.05 ^{+0.92} _{-1.06}	12.89 ^{+5.86} _{-5.83}	3.80
6203980112	12.33	1.324 ^{+0.024} _{-0.024}	0.171 ^{+0.036} _{-0.030}	7.17 ^{+0.50} _{-0.55}	7.75 ^{+1.75} _{-1.51}	6.57
6203980112	12.46	1.481 ^{+0.013} _{-0.013}	0.158 ^{+0.032} _{-0.026}	7.85 ^{+0.45} _{-0.47}	9.36 ^{+2.00} _{-1.61}	8.32
6203980112	12.58	1.513 ^{+0.016} _{-0.015}	0.211 ^{+0.060} _{-0.044}	7.96 ^{+0.56} _{-0.58}	7.16 ^{+2.11} _{-1.57}	6.86
6203980112	12.65	1.426 ^{+0.016} _{-0.015}	0.177 ^{+0.036} _{-0.032}	7.88 ^{+0.43} _{-0.46}	8.04 ^{+1.73} _{-1.55}	8.55
6203980112	12.71	1.413 ^{+0.013} _{-0.013}	0.167 ^{+0.037} _{-0.030}	7.89 ^{+0.48} _{-0.51}	8.47 ^{+1.98} _{-1.61}	7.81
6203980112	12.77	1.390 ^{+0.013} _{-0.013}	0.156 ^{+0.037} _{-0.030}	7.70 ^{+0.47} _{-0.50}	8.91 ^{+2.19} _{-1.81}	7.71
6203980112	12.84	1.411 ^{+0.010} _{-0.010}	0.164 ^{+0.024} _{-0.022}	7.87 ^{+0.33} _{-0.34}	8.62 ^{+1.35} _{-1.22}	11.69
6203980112	12.90	1.491 ^{+0.009} _{-0.009}	0.166 ^{+0.027} _{-0.022}	7.67 ^{+0.31} _{-0.32}	9.00 ^{+1.52} _{-1.24}	12.09
6203980113	13.42	1.398 ^{+0.005} _{-0.005}	0.192 ^{+0.014} _{-0.013}	7.86 ^{+0.16} _{-0.16}	7.27 ^{+0.54} _{-0.51}	24.75
6203980114	14.00	1.392 ^{+0.007} _{-0.007}	0.303 ^{+0.017} _{-0.016}	7.96 ^{+0.14} _{-0.14}	4.59 ^{+0.28} _{-0.27}	27.56
6703010104	14.71	1.624 ^{+0.010} _{-0.010}	0.188 ^{+0.030} _{-0.025}	7.39 ^{+0.31} _{-0.33}	8.62 ^{+1.44} _{-1.19}	11.33
6203980115	15.61	1.348 ^{+0.014} _{-0.014}	0.219 ^{+0.035} _{-0.029}	7.65 ^{+0.36} _{-0.37}	6.15 ^{+1.04} _{-0.89}	10.21
6203980116	16.00	1.398 ^{+0.022} _{-0.021}	0.212 ^{+0.055} _{-0.044}	7.47 ^{+0.52} _{-0.56}	6.59 ^{+1.81} _{-1.48}	6.66
6703010106	19.15	2.298 ^{+0.023} _{-0.022}	0.310 ^{+0.077} _{-0.061}	6.35 ^{+0.33} _{-0.36}	7.42 ^{+1.93} _{-1.53}	8.90
6703010106	19.28	2.770 ^{+0.019} _{-0.019}	0.271 ^{+0.065} _{-0.049}	5.42 ^{+0.28} _{-0.29}	10.23 ^{+2.52} _{-1.91}	9.28
6203980118	19.54	2.371 ^{+0.022} _{-0.022}	0.249 ^{+0.070} _{-0.052}	5.85 ^{+0.38} _{-0.43}	9.53 ^{+2.78} _{-2.09}	6.87
6203980118	19.92	3.051 ^{+0.023} _{-0.023}	0.349 ^{+0.080} _{-0.060}	5.47 ^{+0.28} _{-0.29}	8.74 ^{+2.06} _{-1.56}	9.29
6203980118	19.99	3.271 ^{+0.020} _{-0.020}	0.342 ^{+0.053} _{-0.045}	5.08 ^{+0.21} _{-0.21}	9.55 ^{+1.54} _{-1.31}	11.84
6203980119	20.18	2.683 ^{+0.021} _{-0.021}	0.331 ^{+0.059} _{-0.047}	5.75 ^{+0.27} _{-0.28}	8.11 ^{+1.52} _{-1.21}	10.32
6203980119	20.25	2.844 ^{+0.023} _{-0.021}	0.317 ^{+0.061} _{-0.051}	5.60 ^{+0.26} _{-0.28}	8.98 ^{+1.80} _{-1.53}	10.16
6203980119	20.31	2.700 ^{+0.017} _{-0.017}	0.270 ^{+0.050} _{-0.041}	5.58 ^{+0.27} _{-0.30}	10.00 ^{+1.93} _{-1.60}	9.32
6203980119	20.38	2.601 ^{+0.024} _{-0.023}	0.387 ^{+0.066} _{-0.060}	5.82 ^{+0.25} _{-0.25}	6.73 ^{+1.20} _{-1.10}	11.41
6203980119	20.44	2.605 ^{+0.018} _{-0.017}	0.325 ^{+0.045} _{-0.041}	5.79 ^{+0.22} _{-0.23}	8.01 ^{+1.16} _{-1.05}	12.78
6203980119	20.50	2.634 ^{+0.017} _{-0.017}	0.363 ^{+0.052} _{-0.043}	5.94 ^{+0.23} _{-0.23}	7.26 ^{+1.08} _{-0.91}	12.65
6203980119	20.89	2.111 ^{+0.016} _{-0.016}	0.270 ^{+0.047} _{-0.041}	6.13 ^{+0.27} _{-0.28}	7.82 ^{+1.42} _{-1.23}	11.08
6203980119	20.96	2.023 ^{+0.014} _{-0.014}	0.196 ^{+0.035} _{-0.028}	6.37 ^{+0.31} _{-0.33}	10.32 ^{+1.90} _{-1.55}	9.75
6203980120	21.02	1.991 ^{+0.007} _{-0.007}	0.312 ^{+0.015} _{-0.014}	6.49 ^{+0.10} _{-0.10}	6.39 ^{+0.32} _{-0.31}	32.19

Notes:

rms: root mean square; ν_0 : centroid frequency; Δ : half width at half maximum; σ : significance; QPO: quasiperiodic oscillation[†]: since 60180 MJD

Table 1. continued

Obs ID	day [†]	$\nu_{0,QPO1}$ (Hz)	Δ_{QPO1} (Hz)	rms _{QPO1} (%)	Q _{QPO1}	σ_{QPO1}
6203980121	22.05	2.337 ^{+0.012} _{-0.011}	0.313 ^{+0.034} _{-0.032}	5.91 ^{+0.16} _{-0.16}	7.46 ^{+0.85} _{-0.79}	18.09
6703010107	22.27	2.557 ^{+0.011} _{-0.011}	0.470 ^{+0.025} _{-0.024}	5.92 ^{+0.10} _{-0.10}	5.45 ^{+0.31} _{-0.30}	29.32
6203980122	23.17	2.548 ^{+0.022} _{-0.022}	0.267 ^{+0.054} _{-0.043}	5.73 ^{+0.32} _{-0.34}	9.55 ^{+2.01} _{-1.62}	8.43
6203980122	23.48	3.154 ^{+0.028} _{-0.026}	0.424 ^{+0.085} _{-0.069}	4.95 ^{+0.25} _{-0.26}	7.45 ^{+1.56} _{-1.28}	9.59
6203980130	39.44	6.173 ^{+0.030} _{-0.058}	1.512 ^{+0.158} _{-0.148}	2.03 ^{+0.07} _{-0.07}	4.08 ^{+0.45} _{-0.44}	13.83
6203980131	40.02	6.826 ^{+0.065} _{-0.064}	1.282 ^{+0.236} _{-0.207}	1.63 ^{+0.08} _{-0.08}	5.33 ^{+1.03} _{-0.91}	9.66
6703010113	40.28	6.831 ^{+0.046} _{-0.046}	1.581 ^{+0.120} _{-0.111}	1.62 ^{+0.03} _{-0.04}	4.32 ^{+0.34} _{-0.33}	22.85
6703010114	41.12	9.323 ^{+0.321} _{-0.657}	0.032 ^{+3.599} _{-0.032}	0.59 ^{+0.34} _{-0.36}	295.42 ^{+33700.73} _{-316.25}	0.83
6557020401	41.19	6.849 ^{+0.033} _{-0.033}	1.513 ^{+0.099} _{-0.105}	1.53 ^{+0.03} _{-0.03}	4.53 ^{+0.32} _{-0.34}	22.33
6557020402	42.02	7.007 ^{+0.089} _{-0.093}	1.150 ^{+0.310} _{-0.290}	1.47 ^{+0.10} _{-0.11}	6.09 ^{+1.72} _{-1.62}	6.67
6703010115	42.22	7.057 ^{+0.571} _{-0.104}	0.325 ^{+0.915} _{-0.308}	0.41 ^{+0.12} _{-0.11}	21.68 ^{+62.73} _{-20.83}	1.83

Notes:

rms: root mean square; ν_0 : centroid frequency; Δ : half width at half maximum; σ : significance; QPO: quasiperiodic oscillation

[†]: since 60180 MJD

Table 2. Parameters of the harmonic QPO in the PDS derived from NICER data

Obs ID	day [†]	$\nu_{0;\text{QPO2}}$ (Hz)	Δ_{QPO2} (Hz)	rms _{QPO2} (%)	Q _{QPO2}	σ_{QPO2}
6203980104	4.06	1.088 ^{+0.360} _{-1.088}	1.776 ^{+0.274} _{-0.692}	6.88 ^{+1.49} _{-2.69}	0.61 ^{+0.30} _{-0.85}	1.28
6203980105	5.04	1.423 ^{+0.173} _{-0.234}	1.984 ^{+0.216} _{-0.256}	6.01 ^{+1.09} _{-0.77}	0.72 ^{+0.16} _{-0.21}	3.89
6703010101	5.55	1.720 ^{+0.037} _{-0.047}	0.641 ^{+0.270} _{-0.168}	3.99 ^{+0.53} _{-0.39}	2.68 ^{+1.19} _{-0.77}	5.16
6203980106	6.01	1.878 ^{+0.051} _{-0.052}	2.263 ^{+0.055} _{-0.055}	5.98 ^{+0.13} _{-0.13}	0.83 ± 0.04	22.63
6203980107	7.54	1.948 ^{+0.065} _{-0.065}	2.284 ^{+0.076} _{-0.080}	5.86 ^{+0.17} _{-0.18}	0.85 ± 0.06	15.91
6203980108	8.00	2.163 ^{+0.043} _{-0.043}	2.308 ^{+0.053} _{-0.054}	5.57 ^{+0.10} _{-0.10}	0.94 ± 0.04	27.59
6203980109	9.03	2.210 ^{+0.037} _{-0.037}	2.369 ^{+0.045} _{-0.045}	5.54 ^{+0.08} _{-0.08}	0.93 ± 0.03	33.61
6203980110	10.52	2.320 ^{+0.046} _{-0.048}	2.335 ^{+0.062} _{-0.061}	5.45 ^{+0.11} _{-0.10}	0.99 ± 0.05	26.31
6203980111	11.04	1.995 ^{+0.045} _{-0.046}	2.413 ^{+0.051} _{-0.051}	5.89 ^{+0.11} _{-0.11}	0.83 ± 0.04	26.83
6703010103	11.35	1.894 ^{+0.089} _{-0.095}	2.278 ^{+0.101} _{-0.105}	6.02 ^{+0.26} _{-0.26}	0.83 ± 0.08	11.53
6203980112	12.06	1.677 ^{+0.158} _{-0.168}	2.189 ^{+0.171} _{-0.213}	6.25 ^{+0.54} _{-0.60}	0.77 ^{+0.13} _{-0.15}	5.23
6203980112	12.20	1.095 ^{+0.113} _{-1.095}	2.178 ^{+0.192} _{-0.175}	8.10 ^{+0.40} _{-0.39}	0.50 ^{+0.10} _{-0.54}	10.40
6203980112	12.33	2.249 ^{+0.177} _{-0.196}	2.241 ^{+0.229} _{-0.236}	5.57 ^{+0.45} _{-0.44}	1.00 ^{+0.18} _{-0.19}	6.27
6203980112	12.46	2.596 ^{+0.133} _{-0.147}	2.342 ^{+0.225} _{-0.232}	5.29 ^{+0.27} _{-0.29}	1.11 ^{+0.16} _{-0.17}	9.17
6203980112	12.58	2.838 ^{+0.144} _{-0.156}	2.158 ^{+0.267} _{-0.277}	4.91 ^{+0.31} _{-0.34}	1.32 ^{+0.23} _{-0.24}	7.32
6203980112	12.65	2.548 ^{+0.151} _{-0.171}	2.297 ^{+0.224} _{-0.218}	5.28 ^{+0.33} _{-0.31}	1.11 ^{+0.17} _{-0.18}	8.48
6203980112	12.71	2.627 ^{+0.166} _{-0.176}	2.633 ^{+0.238} _{-0.236}	5.09 ^{+0.29} _{-0.30}	1.00 ^{+0.15} _{-0.16}	8.45
6203980112	12.77	2.434 ^{+0.155} _{-0.173}	2.333 ^{+0.208} _{-0.210}	5.50 ^{+0.33} _{-0.34}	1.04 ^{+0.16} _{-0.17}	8.17
6203980112	12.84	2.465 ^{+0.118} _{-0.127}	2.640 ^{+0.144} _{-0.141}	5.39 ^{+0.22} _{-0.21}	0.93 ± 0.10	12.77
6203980112	12.90	2.610 ^{+0.102} _{-0.110}	2.401 ^{+0.144} _{-0.141}	5.36 ^{+0.20} _{-0.19}	1.09 ± 0.11	13.80
6203980113	13.42	2.520 ^{+0.053} _{-0.053}	2.440 ^{+0.067} _{-0.069}	5.29 ^{+0.10} _{-0.11}	1.03 ± 0.05	24.82
6203980114	14.00	2.571 ^{+0.050} _{-0.051}	2.545 ^{+0.060} _{-0.059}	5.28 ^{+0.09} _{-0.09}	1.01 ± 0.04	28.56
6703010104	14.71	2.859 ^{+0.117} _{-0.122}	2.349 ^{+0.168} _{-0.165}	4.98 ^{+0.22} _{-0.22}	1.22 ± 0.14	11.18
6203980115	15.61	2.363 ^{+0.121} _{-0.130}	2.459 ^{+0.153} _{-0.152}	5.68 ^{+0.26} _{-0.25}	0.96 ± 0.11	11.24
6203980116	16.00	2.485 ^{+0.193} _{-0.212}	2.184 ^{+0.320} _{-0.452}	5.03 ^{+0.42} _{-0.64}	1.14 ^{+0.25} _{-0.33}	3.92
6703010106	19.15	4.633 ^{+0.167} _{-0.181}	2.096 ^{+0.469} _{-0.414}	3.20 ^{+0.26} _{-0.27}	2.21 ^{+0.57} _{-0.52}	5.84
6703010106	19.28	5.400 ^{+0.173} _{-0.224}	2.040 ^{+0.611} _{-0.484}	2.99 ^{+0.25} _{-0.25}	2.65 ^{+0.88} _{-0.74}	5.93
6203980118	19.54	4.484 ^{+0.175} _{-0.229}	1.445 ^{+0.616} _{-0.457}	2.89 ^{+0.36} _{-0.37}	3.10 ^{+1.44} _{-1.14}	3.88
6203980118	19.92	6.043 ^{+0.127} _{-0.137}	1.490 ^{+0.605} _{-0.454}	2.51 ^{+0.23} _{-0.23}	4.06 ^{+1.73} _{-1.33}	5.48
6203980118	19.99	6.451 ^{+0.093} _{-0.089}	0.903 ^{+0.309} _{-0.243}	2.06 ^{+0.16} _{-0.17}	7.15 ^{+2.55} _{-2.02}	6.12
6203980119	20.18	5.139 ^{+0.140} _{-0.172}	2.172 ^{+0.427} _{-0.365}	3.17 ^{+0.18} _{-0.18}	2.37 ^{+0.53} _{-0.48}	8.75
6203980119	20.25	5.415 ^{+0.139} _{-0.153}	1.806 ^{+0.409} _{-0.339}	2.97 ^{+0.20} _{-0.21}	3.00 ^{+0.76} _{-0.65}	7.13
6203980119	20.31	5.381 ^{+0.092} _{-0.091}	1.014 ^{+0.293} _{-0.249}	2.47 ^{+0.21} _{-0.23}	5.31 ^{+1.62} _{-1.39}	5.38
6203980119	20.38	5.080 ^{+0.127} _{-0.146}	2.058 ^{+0.351} _{-0.307}	3.30 ^{+0.18} _{-0.18}	2.47 ^{+0.48} _{-0.44}	9.14
6203980119	20.44	5.091 ^{+0.087} _{-0.107}	1.745 ^{+0.388} _{-0.313}	2.92 ^{+0.15} _{-0.15}	2.92 ^{+0.70} _{-0.58}	9.82
6203980119	20.50	5.247 ^{+0.078} _{-0.083}	1.852 ^{+0.296} _{-0.253}	3.04 ^{+0.13} _{-0.13}	2.83 ^{+0.49} _{-0.43}	11.86
6203980119	20.89	4.103 ^{+0.118} _{-0.143}	2.112 ^{+0.346} _{-0.326}	3.66 ^{+0.23} _{-0.23}	1.94 ± 0.37	7.89
6203980119	20.96	3.701 ^{+0.137} _{-0.162}	2.655 ^{+0.316} _{-0.309}	4.36 ^{+0.22} _{-0.22}	1.39 ± 0.22	10.07
6203980120	21.02	3.827 ^{+0.039} _{-0.040}	2.271 ^{+0.100} _{-0.099}	4.13 ^{+0.07} _{-0.07}	1.69 ± 0.09	28.04
6203980121	22.05	4.465 ^{+0.072} _{-0.082}	2.063 ^{+0.228} _{-0.208}	3.60 ^{+0.12} _{-0.12}	2.16 ^{+0.27} _{-0.26}	14.80

Notes:

rms: root mean square; ν_0 : centroid frequency; Δ : half width at half maximum; σ : significance; QPO: quasiperiodic oscillation[†]: since 60180 MJD

Table 2. continued

Obs ID	day [†]	$\nu_{0,\text{QPO2}}$ (Hz)	Δ_{QPO2} (Hz)	rms _{QPO2} (%)	Q _{QPO2}	σ_{QPO2}
6703010107	22.27	4.970 ^{+0.046} _{-0.047}	2.427 ^{+0.116} _{-0.112}	3.42 ^{+0.06} _{-0.06}	2.05 ^{+0.12} _{-0.11}	28.76
6203980122	23.17	4.995 ^{+0.127} _{-0.165}	2.370 ^{+0.578} _{-0.516}	3.45 ^{+0.20} _{-0.20}	2.11 ^{+0.56} _{-0.53}	8.81
6203980122	23.48	6.280 ^{+0.115} _{-0.111}	1.245 ^{+0.334} _{-0.286}	2.31 ^{+0.17} _{-0.18}	5.05 ^{+1.45} _{-1.25}	6.56
6203980130	39.44	13.753 ^{+0.642} _{-1.787}	0.049 ^{+2.449} _{-0.045}	0.38 ^{+0.14} _{-0.13}	≥ 5.62	1.43
6203980131	40.02	12.489 ^{+1.349} _{-0.272}	0.013 ^{+2.297} _{-0.013}	0.33 ^{+0.11} _{-0.17}	≥ 5.44	0.96
6703010113	40.28	12.708 ^{+0.548} _{-0.122}	≤ 0.738	0.23 ^{+0.06} _{-0.08}	≥ 17.21	1.44
6703010114	41.12	4.310 ^{+1.359} _{-1.031}	3.713 ^{+2.845} _{-2.526}	1.32 ^{+0.27} _{-0.40}	1.16 ^{+1.26} _{-1.07}	1.64
6557020401	41.19	13.748 ^{+0.004} _{-1.619}	0.001 ^{+0.756} _{-0.001}	0.25 ^{+0.06} _{-0.07}	≥ 18.20	1.69
6557020402	42.02	15.140 ^{+0.489} _{-1.403}	0.009 ^{+2.922} _{-0.008}	0.46 ^{+0.18} _{-0.17}	≥ 5.18	1.33
6703010115	42.22	2.753 ^{+0.366} _{-0.627}	0.752 ^{+1.241} _{-0.702}	0.37 ^{+0.14} _{-0.17}	3.66 ^{+6.52} _{-4.25}	1.09

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